

Nature-based reef solution for coastal protection and marine biodiversity enhancement

Deliverable 5.2

Dedicated project page on the beneficiaries' website and social network

Project acronym:	LIFE NatuReef
Project title:	Nature-based reef solution for coastal protection and marine biodiversity enhancement
Programme UE:	LIFE LIFE-2022-SAP-NAT - Nature & Biodiversity - Standard Action
Reference:	LIFE22-NAT-IT-LIFE-NatuReef/101113742
Deliverable:	5.2 - Dedicated project page on the beneficiaries' website and social network
Lead beneficiary:	FLAMINIA
Partners involved:	all
Dissemination level:	public
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ALMA MATER STUDIORUM
UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA

Comune di Ravenna

Parco Delta del Po
Emilia-Romagna

PROAMBIENTE
innovation & environment

FONDAZIONE FLAMINIA
PER L'UNIVERSITÀ
IN ROMAGNA

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Project page on the beneficiaries' website and social network

Each beneficiary has a page dedicated to the project on their website. These pages all link to the main project website which is hosted by the servers of the Alma Mater Studiorum University of Bologna, the project's coordinating partner.

Main project website

This is the main project website; it is kept updated with project activities, news and outcomes. It is available in both Italian and English. It is permanently hosted by the servers of the Alma Mater Studiorum University of Bologna on the premise of the coordinator. It is linked to the project site hosted in the European Union database and to the sites of all the partners involved. Communication team, from the beneficiary partner FLAMINIA has access to implement contents, according to the Communication and Dissemination Plan (Project Deliverable D5.1).

<https://site.unibo.it/life-natureef/>

The screenshot shows the website's header with the LIFE NatuReef logo, the Life and Natura 2000 logos, and language selection buttons for IT and EN. A navigation menu includes HOME, PROJECT, ACTIVITIES, and CONTACTS. The main content area features an aerial photograph of a coastal area with a river mouth and a reef. To the right of the image is a text block with the following content:

Nature-based reef solution for coastal protection and marine biodiversity enhancement

LIFE NatuReef aims to apply at demonstration level the best practices available to the restoration of native oyster and sabellariid reefs, seeding the native species in a rare non-urbanized coastal stretches of the northern Adriatic coasts: the Bevano river mouth (Ravenna municipality, Emilia-Romagna Region, Italy), which is a SAC and SPA under the EU Natura 2000 (IT4070009 - Ortazzo, Ortazzino, Foce del Torrente Bevano).

Project page at UNIBO

At the website of the beneficiary partner **Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna**, the LIFE NatuReef project page is listed among the research projects, LIFE project session.

Path: Home > Research > Competences, projects, initiatives > Research projects - LIFE > LIFE 2021-2027 > LIFE NatuReef

<https://www.unibo.it/en/research/projects-and-initiatives/research-projects-life/life-2021-2027/602/724/18253>

The screenshot shows the project page for LIFE NatuReef on the Alma Mater Studiorum University of Bologna website. The page features a navigation menu with categories like HOME, UNIVERSITY, TEACHING, RESEARCH, and UNIVERSITY AND SOCIETY. The main content area includes the project title "LIFE NatuReef", a description "Nature-based reef solution for coastal protection and marine biodiversity enhancement", an abstract, and project details such as the team leader (Massimo Ponti), departments involved, coordinator, other participants, total EU contribution (€1,909,832.00), project duration (48 months), start date (01/07/2023), and end date (30/06/2027). A link to the Cordis webpage is also provided.

Project page at RAVENNA

At the website of the beneficiary partner **Comune di Ravenna**, the LIFE NatuReef project page is listed among the International and European projects and activities on environment and sustainable development.

Path: Home > Aree tematiche > Politiche europee, rapporti internazionali e PNRR > Progetti europei e internazionali > Archivio Progetti > Ambiente e Sviluppo Sostenibile > 2023-2027 LIFE NATUREEF – Nature-based reef solution for coastal protection and marine biodiversity enhancement

<https://www.comune.ra.it/aree-tematiche/politiche-europee-e-rapporti/politiche-europee-e-progetti/progetti-terminati/ambiente-e-sviluppo-sostenibile/life-naturereef-nature-based-reef-solution-for-coastal-protection-and-marine-biodiversity-enhancement/>

The screenshot shows the website of the Comune di Ravenna. At the top, there is a red navigation bar with the Comune di Ravenna logo and social media icons. Below this is a search bar and a menu with categories like 'IL COMUNE', 'SERVIZI', 'TRASPARENZA', 'BANDI, CONCORSI', 'STAMPA E COMUNICAZIONE', 'URP', and 'TURISMO'. The main content area features a breadcrumb trail: Home > Aree tematiche > Politiche europee, rapporti internazionali e PNRR > Progetti europei e internazionali > Archivio Progetti > Ambiente e Sviluppo Sostenibile > 2023-2027 LIFE NATUREEF – Nature-based reef solution for coastal protection and marine biodiversity enhancement. The title of the page is '2023-2027 LIFE NATUREEF – Nature-based reef solution for coastal protection and marine biodiversity enhancement'. Below the title are social media sharing icons for Facebook and Twitter. The LIFE NatuReef logo is prominently displayed. The text describes the project's goal: to favor the formation of reefs (scogliere marine) formed by native oyster and sabellariid species, installed in the sea area in front of the mouth of the Bevano river. It lists the species *Ostrea edulis*, *Sabellaria alveolata*, and *Sabellaria spinulosa* and explains their role in forming natural barriers against coastal erosion. It also mentions the importance of oyster reefs for marine biodiversity and the project's contribution to climate change adaptation and cultural services.

SCHEDA TECNICA:

Programma: LIFE – Natura e Biodiversità, bando 2022

Reference: LIFE22-NAT-IT-LIFE-NatuReef/101113742

Acronimo: LIFE22-NAT-IT-LIFE NatuReef

Project page at PROAMBIENTE

At the website of the beneficiary partner **PROAMBIENTE S.c.r.l.**, the LIFE NatuReef project page is listed among the ongoing projects.

Path: Home > Projects > ongoing

<https://www.consorzioproambiente.it/en/projects/in-corso/349-life-natureef>

The screenshot shows the website for the LIFE NatuReef project. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for ABOUT US, EXPERTISE, PRODUCTS&SERVICES, PROJECTS (highlighted), MEDIA, and CONTACTS. The main heading is "LIFE NatuReef" with the LIFE and NATURA 2000 logos. Below this is a sub-heading: "Nature-based reef solution for coastal protection and marine biodiversity enhancement". The text describes the project as a European initiative to restore oyster and sabellid reefs at the mouth of the Bevano River. It lists goals such as creating an oyster reef, stimulating the development of sabellid worm reefs, and enhancing marine biodiversity. On the right side, there is a sidebar with "Tematiche" (Topics) including Water Monitoring, Air Quality Monitoring, Agricultural Systems, Water Treatment, Instrument Development and Sensors, and Project Management. Below that is a "Related Articles" section.

Project page at DELTA_PO

At the website of the beneficiary partner **Ente di Gestione per i Parchi e la Biodiversità - Delta del Po**, the LIFE NatuReef project page is listed among the ongoing European projects.

Path: Home > Ente > Progetti Europei e finanziamenti > Progetti Europei > Progetti Europei in Corso

<https://www.parcodeltapo.it/it/pagina.php?id=143>

The screenshot shows the website of Parco Delta del Po Emilia-Romagna. The navigation bar includes links for 'Albo Online', 'Amministrazione trasparente', 'Bandi di gara / avvisi', 'Procedure nulla osta e valutazione di incidenza', 'Come fare per...', and 'Contatti'. The main header features the park's logo and the text 'NATURA E TERRITORIO', 'VIVERE IL PARCO', and 'ENTE'. A large landscape image of a coastal area with water and vegetation is displayed. Below the image, the breadcrumb trail reads: 'Home >> Ente >> Progetti Europei e finanziamenti >> Progetti Europei >> Progetti Europei in Corso'. The main content area is titled 'Life NatuReef' and describes it as a 'Nature-based reef solution for coastal protection and marine biodiversity enhancement'. Key details include: Programme UE: LIFE; LIFE-2022-SAP-NAT - Nature & Biodiversity - Standard Action; Riferimento: LIFE22-NAT-IT-LIFE-NatuReef/101113742; Durata: 1/07/2023 - 30/06/2027; Budget: € 3'183'057; Contributo europeo: € 1'909'832 (60%). A section titled 'Il Progetto in breve' explains that the project aims to restore oyster and mussel reefs at the mouth of the Torrente Bevano, which provide natural coastal protection and enhance biodiversity. The project is described as a sustainable laboratory for 'good practices' applied for the first time in the Adriatic. The overall goal is to restore and regenerate nature. A small image of the LIFE NatuReef logo is also present, credited to AAVV.

Project page at FLAMINIA

At the website of the beneficiary partner **Fondazione FLAMINIA**, the LIFE NatuReef project page is listed among the ongoing European projects.

Path: Home > Progetti > LIFE NatuReef

<https://cifla.it/progetti/life-natureef/>

LIFE NatuReef

Nature-based reef solution for coastal protection and marine biodiversity enhancement

[English version](#)

DESCRIZIONE PROGETTO

LIFE NatuReef è un progetto europeo per ripristinare le antiche scogliere di ostriche e sabellarie alla foce del Torrente Bevano.

Queste scogliere sono «biocostruzioni» naturali che forniscono una serie di beni e servizi ecosistemici, tra cui il ripristino degli habitat sottomarini, il potenziamento della biodiversità, la protezione degli habitat costieri dalle mareggiate e dai processi di erosione, in un'ottica di contrasto e adattamento ai cambiamenti climatici.

Il progetto è un'importante iniziativa per la conservazione dell'ambiente e lo sviluppo sostenibile e rappresenta un laboratorio di "buone pratiche" applicato per la prima volta nel mare Adriatico.

LIFE NatuReef è la natura che ripara e rigenera.

SCHEDA TECNICA

Tipologia: Bando Competitivo

Programme UE: LIFE

LIFE-2022-SAP-NAT – Nature & Biodiversity – Standard Action

Riferimento: LIFE22-NAT-IT-LIFE-NatuReef/101113742

Durata

1/07/2023 – 30/06/2027

Budget

€ 3'183'057

Contributo europeo: € 1'909'832 (60%)

Project page at RCI

At the website of the associated partner **Reef Check Italia**, the LIFE NatuReef project page is listed among the Mediterranean projects and activities “Reef Check Med”.

Path: Home > Italiano > Reef Check Med > LIFE NatuReef

<https://www.reefcheckmed.org/italiano/reef-check-med/life-natureef/>

The screenshot shows the Italian version of the Reef Check website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with language options: ENGLISH, ITALIANO, ESPAÑOL, FRANÇAIS, DEUTSCH, HRVATSKI, E/А/И/Н/И/К/А, and TRAINERLOGIN. The main header features a large underwater photograph of a coral reef with the text "REEF CHECK Mediterranean Sea". Below this, a sidebar on the left lists various project categories and years. The main content area includes the LIFE NatuReef logo, a description of the project as a "Nature-based reef solution for coastal protection and marine biodiversity enhancement", and a green box containing key project details: Programme UE: LIFE, LIFE-2022-SAP-NAT – Nature & Biodiversity - Standard Action, Riferimento: LIFE22-NAT-IT-LIFE-NatuReef/101113742, Durata: 1/07/2023 – 30/06/2027, Budget: € 3'183'057, Contributo europeo: € 1'909'832 (60%), and Website: <https://site.unibo.it/life-natureef/>. At the bottom, there is a section titled "IL PROGETTO IN BREVE" with a brief description of the project's goal to restore oyster and sabellid reefs.